

Spark optimization techniques: A Developer's view

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

Nowadays, the evolution and scale of data and computation enables us to do a lot of progress with data analytics. On the same note, algorithms innovation make calculations run much faster.

However, there is an issue here. All these progresses will not be enough without knowing how to use Spark efficiently. Thus, there is a huge difference between writing an optimized code, and writing a sloppy one.

2. Aim

To bring awareness to data engineers of the importance of using optimized Spark code, to avoid heavy shuffling of data, RDDs, and out of memory errors.

3. Material and methods

Here are some techniques, tips and tricks for writing optimized Spark Code:

Avoid shuffling by partitioning the data correctly and choosing the right transformations

An example of this would be using ReduceByKey (shuffling data once per partition) rather than GroupByKey(which shuffles the data multiple times for each partition)

The less stages of shuffling you have, the faster your data runs.

Let Spark optimize your code by avoiding RDD.

RDD's are immutable collection of objects which provide in-memory computation of your data. However, there are issues with them, as they do not provide any schema of your data, and thus cannot be evolved in terms of complexity.

Move runtime errors to compile-time by using Datasets as opposed to Dataframes.

Runtime errors are hard to trace and debug, therefore using Dataframes is not optimal and can cause issues later on. A Dataset would be more efficient and appropriate to use in this case.

Set the right parameters for the spark jobs: number of executors, memory allocation, driver memory, and more. This allows data engineers to be in control of their data and manage it properly

Finally, analyze various code snippets and optimize them.

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4. Results

Using the above techniques to optimize your Spark code results in faster executed code, being able to catch and handle critical errors at compile time, not having to shuffle the data so many times (thus taking a long time and resources), and managing memory efficiently (to avoid out of memory errors)

5. Conclusions

According to the results of this study, it has been proven that optimization of Spark code by using the above methods is an effective and necessary process, in order to ensure that the resulting data ends up being fast executed, correct, cohesive, and scalable.

6. Keywords

Spark, RDD, Dataset, Dataframe, optimization, memory, executors, shuffling, partition

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